

AI4

D4.2 - First release of the AI Platform as a Service

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable comprises a demonstrator concerning the first release of the AI4EOSC AI Platform as a Service (PaaS). In line with the need to update the architecture of the platform according to the rapidly growing scientific and technological advances, this document summarizes all the developments performed in the components implemented and available in the first AI4EOSC software Platform release (AI4EOSC 1).

Activities have been carried out to implement a federated cloud platform enabling the exploitation of different cloud sites, transparently by the user.

A PaaS layer providing services to deploy in an automatic way the AI4EOSC core components has been implemented and made available and the OSCAR cluster (and related services) can be deployed in a few steps.

Features have been developed, implemented and made available for OSCAR such as the exposition of service-related API, the preload of docker images and the multitenancy support by leveraging the adoption of OIDC protocol.

The federated training has been implemented and the federated server has been made available to users as a tool via the AI4EOSC dashboard.

Last but not least, interactive development tools has been implemented and made available in the AI4EOSC platform providing for developers two of the most popular IDEs: JupyterLab and Visual Studio Code. Looking ahead, this deliverable also updates the roadmap for the AI4EOSC 2 explaining the deviations from the initial plan.

1. - INTRODUCTION

During the first year of the AI4EOSC project, important activities have been carried out to provide a set of components and functionalities to be provided to the final users. The list of such components has been collected and described in the deliverable D4.1 [1], where the initial implementation plan was established, both for the first release (AI4EOSC 1) and for the AI4EOSC 2 release. The present deliverable seeks to delve into these components describing the work carried out on each of them, as well as the deviations from the initially defined plan, in some cases followed by advances made ahead of schedule.

1.1 - SCOPE OF THE DOCUMENT

The main goal of the AI4EOSC project is to deliver an enhanced set of services for the development and deployment of Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning and Deep Learning (AI/ML/DL) models and applications in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) context. The AI4EOSC platform, as an evolution of the DEEP-Hybrid-Datacloud platform (DEEP-HDC) [2], will be focused on enhancing the current DEEP services and will make use of advanced new features such as distributed, split, and federated learning, provenance metadata, event-driven data processing technologies, or the provisioning of AI/ML/DL services based on serverless computing.

The project will place a special emphasis on ensuring that all the research results and sub-products (data, models, metadata, publications, etc.) adhere to the FAIR and scientific principles.

The vision of the AI4EOSC project is to increase the service offer in the EU landscape by expanding the EOSC ecosystem to support the effective usage of state-of-the-art AI techniques by the research community.

This document is a demonstrator of the evolution of the components presented in the Deliverable 4.1 "Implementation plan" [1] and implemented within the AI Platform as a Service architecture.

1.2 - STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

This document is structured as follows: Section 2 provides a detailed description of the AI4EOSC components that have been used and evolved to build the first release of the AI4EOSC platform. Section 3 will describe the current roadmap for the AI4EOSC release 2 by confirming or updating the expected evolution for each of the components as

explained in the initial implementation plan deployed in D4.1. The deviations from the original plan are also exposed and discussed. In addition the expected deviations for the AI4EOSC 2 release are also provided. Finally, Section 4 outlines the conclusions obtained.

2. - AI PLATFORM AS A SERVICE

In the following section, we present a concise overview of the technologies chosen for each of those components and the evolution of the related functionalities during the past 18 months. Improvements or even new functionalities are expected with the second release in order to accomplish the requirements during the lifetime of the project. In addition, in [Figure 1](#) the architecture of the platform together with its components and their relations is presented, highlighting the WP4 tasks involved.

Figure 1: AI Platform as a Service components and interactions with the other components of the project

2.1 - IDENTITY AND ACCESS MANAGEMENT

EGI Check-in [10] has been adopted as a central authentication and authorization service within the AI4EOSC platform and related components.

EGI Check-in is a service provided by the European Grid Infrastructure (EGI²), which is a federation of European national grid computing initiatives. EGI Check-in is a single sign-on (SSO) authentication and authorization service, based on OpenID Connect, that allows users to access various grid computing resources and services using a single set of credentials. The usage of this system is in line with the AAI interoperability guidelines, especially the AARC blueprint³, therefore its adoption allows an easy integration path with the EOSC core services and the future EOSC EU Node.

EGI Check-in provides authorization mechanisms, ensuring that users have appropriate permissions to access the resources and services they require within the EGI infrastructure. AI4EOSC components that require authentication have been integrated with the EGI Check-in, as described in the corresponding sections.

2.2 - WORKLOAD MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

Federated Cloud Environment

For the first release of the Workload Management System aligned with the D4.1 Implementation Plan [1], Nomad [11] and Consul [12] infrastructures have been deployed and Traefik [13] has been used as load balancer and reverse proxy. Two clusters have already been deployed at IFCA (CSIC), IISAS and TUBITAK sites by leveraging the Ansible [14] automation mechanism to create/add new clusters. In particular, the Ansible recipes allow the automation of the following operational tasks::

- Creation of an initial federated cluster from scratch.
- Creation and joining of a new site to the federated cluster.
- Updating Consul and Nomad versions on the cluster nodes.

The recipes are maintained in an online public repository (<https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-ansible/>) and will serve as the basis for the rest of tasks in WP4 that deal with the management of the platform layer (T4.1, T4.2 and T4.3).

Currently the production cluster is managing more than 700 CPU cores, 2 TB of RAM and more than 35 GPUs. [Figure 2](#) shows the reference Consul/Nomad architecture for one datacenter.

² European Grid Infrastructure - <https://www.egi.eu/>

³ The AARC Blueprint Architecture (BPA) - <https://aarc-project.eu/guidelines/>

Additional clusters are expected to join the AI4EOSC platform during the project lifetime. This will increase fault-tolerance and provide users with additional computing resources for developing their applications.

Figure 2: Reference Consul/Nomad architecture⁴

The referenced federated environment deployed in the AI4EOSC project can be seen in [Figure 3](#). This implementation enables us to build a robust, scalable environment that can operate effectively by exploiting multiple resources and enhancing resilience, scalability, flexibility and interoperability in a transparent way.

Each data center must have at least one consul and nomad server, which will be in charge of communications with the rest of the data centers. To avoid conflicting updates, a server node is designated as a leader through the Raft protocol, and it will be responsible for processing cluster transactions.

⁴<https://developer.hashicorp.com/nomad/tutorials/enterprise/production-reference-architecture-vm-with-consul>

Figure 3: Federated Consul/Nomad architecture

In addition, a set of auxiliary functionalities have been developed for the operations of Nomad:

- Email Service: This service is responsible for notifying the authors of a job when it is deployed after having been queued for a long time.
- Docuum: This service allows us to limit the space used by Docker images within a node, applying an LRU policy for replacements.

Moreover, for maintenance purposes, we have developed the following tasks that are executed periodically:

- Empty trash folder in Docker containers.
- Delete nomad jobs that have been dead for a long time.
- Delete pending jobs that are not in queued, starting, or unknown states.

Users do not have direct access to this platform layer (i.e. the Nomad API, Consul and Traefki APIs), but to the AI4-PAPI component (developed within WP5 and described in D5.2), where authentication and authorization is performed. This API hides the underlying platform implementation to the users, so that it can be easily replaced with another technology if needed. Moreover, AI4-PAPI allows us to implement more complex

features (like sidecar containers, privileged containers, etc.) transparently for the users, allowing us to deliver a more feature-rich platform.

2.3 - PAAS ORCHESTRATION AND PROVISIONING

For the first AI4EOSC release (AI4EOSC 1), the following functionalities have been implemented:

Support for automatic deployment of the Workload Management System (Nomad)

The automatic deployment of the core components of the Workload Management System, i.e. Nomad [11] and Consul [12] have been implemented by means of a TOSCA [15] template and Ansible Roles, developed by CSIC and UPV. The TOSCA template provides a standardized blueprint for the deployment of Nomad and Consul, while the Ansible roles automate the configuration of the infrastructure provisioned through the Infrastructure Manager [35]. This ensures that the deployment process is fast, reliable, and repeatable, reducing the risk of errors and minimizing the time and effort required for manual deployment.

Support for automatic deployment of OSCAR clusters

As in the previous case, an OSCAR [16] cluster can be deployed through the PaaS Orchestrator by means of a TOSCA template and Ansible roles. The Orchestrator interacts with the Infrastructure Manager to provision and configure the infrastructure. OSCAR is built on top of a Kubernetes [17] cluster together with the MinIO [18] object storage service, as described in section 2.4. Proper configuration has been applied in order to:

- Let the services interact among them;
- Create a proper TLS certificate using the Let's Encrypt [19] Certification Authority.

PaaS components for provisioning

PaaS AAI mechanism: The Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure service for the PaaS components layer is provided by the INDIGO Identity and Access Management Service [3] (INDIGO-IAM) that leverages the OIDC and OAuth2.0 [9] protocols.

- Added the configuration to support Normal users (they can login to the INDIGO-IAM service, register client applications that use the INDIGO-IAM for authentication and link external accounts to their account and Administrators (they have administrative privileges within the INDIGO-IAM organization).
- Added EGI Check-in as a federated IdP enabling the access to EGI users.

Latest release: <https://github.com/indigo-iam/iam/releases/tag/v1.8.3>

PaaS Orchestrator [20]: built with Java technologies and on the open-source workflow manager “Flowable” [21], the Orchestrator allows federating heterogeneous resource providers and orchestrate the deployment of TOSCA templates, selecting the best provider according to criteria like the data location, the Service Level Agreement (SLA) and monitoring information. It provides a set of APIs to create, monitor and manage the deployments.

- The PaaS monitoring and metering service has been designed and is under development. It will collect metrics from different sources and organize the information to provide a rank of the different providers for deployment submission.
- A functionality for deployment based on data placement is under study and a prototype will be provided in the next release.
- The functionality to manage both creation and deletion of IAM clients directly from the orchestrator has been added.

Last release: <https://github.com/indigo-dc/orchestrator/releases/tag/v2.8.0-FINAL>

PaaS Dashboard [22]: it’s a Flask [23] application with a SQL database (MySQL) that enables users to interact easily with the services of the PaaS, particularly the Orchestrator, to create TOSCA-based deployments. The dashboard provides a user-friendly interface for managing and monitoring deployments.

- The TOSCA template for OSCAR deployment has been prepared, together with the related tosca types, and the graphical button for an easy deployment has been added. The graphical representation related to the automatic deployment of OSCAR is shown in [Figure 4](#) where the workflow is reported.

Latest release: <https://baltig.infn.it/ai4eosc/tosca-templates/-/blob/master/oscar.yaml>

- The TOSCA template for NOMAD cluster deployment has been prepared, together with the related tosca types, and is under testing.
- Modification to in-use template as well as template for new deployment will be added in the next release.

Latest release: <https://github.com/indigo-dc/orchestrator-dashboard/releases/tag/v3.2.1>

Infrastructure Manager (IM) [24]: it’s an open-source framework designed to simplify the access and usability of IaaS clouds. It automates the selection, deployment, configuration, monitoring and update of virtualized infrastructures..

- Support for infrastructure names defined by users. In previous versions, the user could only refer to an infrastructure using the internal ID assigned by the IM service. In the latest release, the user can also access it using a name assigned by them.
- Added support to Ansible collections. In previous versions, the IM enabled the users to specify the set of Ansible roles used in their playbooks, so the IM automatically installs them before the execution of the playbooks. In this new version, this support has also been extended to Ansible collections.
- Improved OSCAR service deployment. As the OSCAR service definition evolves, the IM also has to be extended to support it. In particular, in this latest release, the GPU support has been added.

Latest release: <https://github.com/grycap/im/releases/tag/v1.15.0>

Figure 4: AI platform customization via resource orchestration

2.4 - AI AS A SERVICE

For this project, the OSCAR [16] platform is used to support the scalable inference of pre-trained AI models from the AI4EOSC marketplace [25].

OSCAR is an open-source platform built on Kubernetes for event-driven data-processing of serverless applications packaged as Docker containers. To trigger the execution of

these applications, OSCAR receives events from object-storage systems such as MinIO⁵ or dCache⁶ and creates the corresponding jobs that are executed on an elastic Kubernetes cluster for workload adaptation. Synchronous invocations of OSCAR services can also be performed for faster AI inference on an auto-scaled set of containers.

The features developed in OSCAR for AI4EOSC are summarized as follows:

- **Exposed services:** This feature allows the deployment of services that expose their own API as an OSCAR service so users can directly interact, for example, with the DEEPaaS API [36] of the AI4EOSC models for inference.

Latest release for DEEPaaS API:

<https://github.com/ai4os/DEEPaaS/releases/tag/2.2.0>

- **Image fetching:** A method of pre-loading Docker images in the nodes of an OSCAR cluster upon an OSCAR service creation has been implemented to mitigate *cold start* (delay attributed to resource provisioning on the first invocations).
- **Initial multitenancy support:** By leveraging the use of OIDC, exemplified with the integration with EGI check-in for authentication, multitenancy has been implemented using the IDs associated with an EGI account to isolate the services and MinIO buckets between users without the need for a database for user management.
- **Integration AI4-PAPI - OSCAR (in progress):** Integration with the AI4EOSC Platform API (AI4-PAPI) [34] to be able to interact with the OSCAR cluster through it.

Latest release: <https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-papi/releases/tag/v1.0.0>

Latest OSCAR release: <https://github.com/grycap/oscar/releases/tag/v3.0.0>.

The OSCAR cluster has been deployed on the NCG-INGRID-PT cloud site, part of AI4EOSC platform.. Moreover, as a method of authentication, EGI Check-in is used so that only users from the virtual organization (VO) associated with the project have access to the cluster. [Figure 5](#) shows the login interface for the AI4EOSC cluster⁷. Based on OIDC, this approach can also be extended to support the INDIGO-IAM.

⁵ MinIO object storage <https://min.io/>

⁶ dCache distributed storage for scientific data <https://www.dcache.org/>

⁷ Link to the AI4EOSC cluster <https://inference.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/ui/>

Figure 5: AI4EOOSC OSCAR service user interface

Some models have already been created as a service on the cluster so users can test the inference process, which can be done both from the platform's web-based UI and the OSCAR command line as well (`oscar-cli`⁸). These models can be found on the AI4EOOSC dashboard. In particular, the deployed models are the Plant species classifier⁹ and the Body pose detector¹⁰ ones.

2.5 - FEDERATED TRAINING

One of the AI4EOOSC project objectives is to provide advanced features for the deployment and development of machine and deep learning models in a distributed way over different clients. In such respect, a set of tools and services have been provided to perform the training of such models under a federated learning architecture.

For this purpose, a federated learning server has been implemented using the Python library Flower [26]. The implementation of the Federated Learning (FL) server can be found in [27] together with some client code examples.

Latest version of the Federated Learning (FL) server:
<https://github.com/deephdc/federated-server>.

This server can be deployed using two IDEs (Interactive Development Environments), JupyterLab [28] or Visual Studio Code [29], which allow more interaction with the

⁸ <https://docs.oscar.grycap.net/oscar-cli/>

⁹ <https://dashboard.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/marketplace/modules/deep-oc-plants-classification-tf>

¹⁰ <https://dashboard.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/marketplace/modules/deep-oc-posenet-tf>

development environment (specifically in order to be able to stop training, restart it, modify variables, etc). In case there is no interest in using these IDEs, the service can be started as "fedserver", which allows the opening of a terminal to monitor the process (see the different clients that are connecting, the evolution of the training process, if any failure occurs or any client disconnects, etc.).

It is important to stress here that the federated server is available to users as a tool in the AI4EOSC dashboard, having made a distinction between modules and tools (see [Figure 6](#)).

Figure 6: AI4EOSC dashboard tools: federated learning server

When starting the FL server, the user has to set up the general configuration requirements such as: deployment name and description, custom domain, service to run (fedserver, Jupyter or Visual Studio Code), Docker image and tag. Then, the hardware requirements also have to be defined: number of CPUs, RAM and disk size. After that, the FL server is configured with the options shown in the description displayed with the *help button* as in [Figure 7](#):

Figure 7: AI4EOSC federated server configuration

Once the federated server is deployed, the user can start it in order to be able to connect the different clients involved. These clients can be allocated and started in other AI4EOSC deployments, in other cloud instances or just locally. The code for defining a client and the one for connecting with the server are shown in [Figure 8](#) and in [Figure 9](#) respectively. As shown in [Figure 9](#), the clients must introduce the endpoint of the FL server deployed in AI4EOSC for connecting. In addition, [Figure 8](#) illustrates the simplicity of creating a Flower client, needed to perform the federated learning training, thus becoming very easy for the final user to switch from a centralized to a distributed approach using the FL server made available in AI4EOSC.

```
# Flower client
class Client1(fl.client.NumPyClient):
    def get_parameters(self, config):
        return model.get_weights()

    def fit(self, parameters, config):
        model.set_weights(parameters)
        model.fit(x_train, y_train, epochs=5, batch_size=16)
        return model.get_weights(), len(x_train), {}

    def evaluate(self, parameters, config):
        model.set_weights(parameters)
        loss, accuracy = model.evaluate(x_test, y_test)
        return loss, len(x_test), {"accuracy": accuracy}
```

Figure 8: Example of a Flower client

```
# Start -> connecting with the server
# UUID of the deployment of the FL server (AI4EOSC):
uuid = 'ac4d8ad0-c0db-11ee-aa18-0242ac120004'
end_point = f"fedserver-{uuid}.deployments.cloud.ai4eosc.eu"
fl.client.start_numpy_client(
    server_address=f"{end_point}:443",
    client=Client1(),
    root_certificates=Path(certifi.where()).read_bytes()
)
```

Figure 9: Starting the connection of a client with the server deployed with the given deployment UUID

In [Figure 10](#) the evolution from the server side (deployed in the AI4EOSC platform) can be seen concerning an example in which three clients are connected for performing the FL training (only the first round is shown for displaying purposes).

```
INFO flwr 2024-02-01 09:17:58,840 | app.py:162 | Starting Flower server, config: ServerConfig(num_rounds=10, round_timeout=None)
INFO flwr 2024-02-01 09:17:58,848 | app.py:175 | Flower ECE: gRPC server running (10 rounds), SSL is disabled
INFO flwr 2024-02-01 09:17:58,848 | server.py:89 | Initializing global parameters
INFO flwr 2024-02-01 09:17:58,848 | server.py:276 | Requesting initial parameters from one random client
INFO flwr 2024-02-01 09:18:07,666 | server.py:280 | Received initial parameters from one random client
INFO flwr 2024-02-01 09:18:07,666 | server.py:91 | Evaluating initial parameters
INFO flwr 2024-02-01 09:18:07,666 | server.py:104 | FL starting
DEBUG flwr 2024-02-01 09:18:17,565 | server.py:222 | fit_round 1: strategy sampled 3 clients (out of 3)
DEBUG flwr 2024-02-01 09:19:20,002 | server.py:236 | fit_round 1 received 3 results and 0 failures
WARNING flwr 2024-02-01 09:19:20,033 | fedavg.py:242 | No fit_metrics_aggregation_fn provided
DEBUG flwr 2024-02-01 09:19:20,033 | server.py:173 | evaluate_round 1: strategy sampled 3 clients (out of 3)
DEBUG flwr 2024-02-01 09:19:21,367 | server.py:187 | evaluate_round 1 received 3 results and 0 failures
```

Figure 10: Federated learning training. Starting the training and first round. Server side (deployed in AI4EOSC)

Finally, when the number of rounds of the federated training has been completed, the user will be able to see the duration of the training as well as the aggregated metrics and the aggregated loss according to the number of rounds. This can be monitored from the server side, deployed in the AI4EOSC platform. Only at this point, in each client, the global model can now be tested and used in production.

2.6 - INTERACTIVE DEVELOPMENT TOOLS

To facilitate the development of new modules, the AI4EOSC platform offers software templates, or cookiecutters [30], where the Cookiecutter command-line tool can be used to create a software repository based on the template. To simplify further how new projects can be generated, a web service, AI Project Templates, is offered to users for creating repositories based on the Cookiecutter templates via a web UI: a user has to authenticate with EGI Check-In and fill the web form corresponding to the template. Then the Cookiecutter tool runs in the background and the generated project is offered for download (Figure 11). The web service is a subset of a more general service, Templates Hub¹¹.

Latest version of the AI4EOSC Project templates: <https://templates.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/>

Figure 11: AI Project Templates offers three templates (left). To generate a software project based on the selected template, one fills the web form (right)

Furthermore, the AI4EOSC platform provides for developers two of the most popular IDEs; i.e., JupyterLab and Visual Studio Code (Figure 12). Both IDEs are web-based and have a modular design with a lot of extensions available to expand their basic

¹¹ <https://templates.services.fedcloud.eu/>

functionality. In AI4EOSC, Visual Studio Code is being deployed with several pre-installed extensions to support Jupyter notebooks.

Figure 12: Selecting IDE in container deployment options

The provided IDEs are secured with TLS & HTTPS connection and user-defined password. The TLS termination is configured in the Traefik reverse proxy, which also ensures connection to IDEs from anywhere. Users define passwords in the AI4EOSC Dashboard in the Deployment options panel, where they also choose their preferred IDE. Source code can be synchronized with Git repositories either from an IDE's command line (both IDEs) or IDE extension (Visual Studio Code only). Debugging functionality is provided to developers in both IDEs. To start with the development, the AI4OS Development Environment module¹² is provided in AI4EOSC Marketplace for deployment.

Examples of JupyterLab and VS Code environments are shown in [Figure 13](#) and [Figure 14](#), respectively.

¹² <https://dashboard.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/marketplace/modules/deep-oc-generic-dev/train>

Figure 13: JupyterLab environment running in deployed container

Figure 14: VS code environment running in deployed container

3. - ROADMAP EVALUATION

This section evaluates how the roadmap stated in the Deliverable D4.1 has been realized so far, specifying when changes from the initial plan have occurred. To do so, [Table 1](#) shows the different components and actions planned for AI4EOOSC 1 and their status and description (if needed). In order to detail the level of compliance or implementation of the different actions or components, in [Table 1](#) the green bullet (●) represents that the component is ready, the blue bullet (●) that it is under testing phase and the orange one (●) that it is under development or is a prototype.

Component/Actions	Status + Description
Federated Service Catalogue/ design and implementation	● The service has been designed and a prototype is under evaluation. It will be launched in the next release.
PaaS Monitoring and Metering/design and implementation	● The service has been designed and a prototype is under evaluation. It will be released in the next release.
PaaS Orchestrator/Nomad deployment	● The automatic deployment of Nomad + Consul has been designed and implemented in the PaaS Orchestrator.
PaaS Orchestrator/OSCAR deployment	● The automatic deployment of OSCAR on top of Kubernetes has been designed and implemented in the PaaS Orchestrator. MinIO object storage service has been also implemented in the related environment.
PaaS Orchestrator/Federated Catalogue integration	● The service is on its prototypical version and will be integrated in the next release.
Cloud Provider Ranker/algorithm update	● The dataset has been defined and a number of algorithms are under evaluation. It will be released in the next release.
Infrastructure Manager automation + OSCAR integration	● OSCAR components automation has been implemented via the IM. The IM can deploy OSCAR services defined in TOSCA templates.
OSCAR manager/Reduced cold start	● To mitigate cold start a method for prefetching Docker images in the Kubernetes nodes when creating an OSCAR service has been implemented.
OSCAR Manager/Interfaces + Libraries	● The following features have been integrated in OSCAR: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Deployment of services that expose their own API as an OSCAR service. ● Initial multitenancy support.
Workload Management System implementation and automation	● Nomad and Consul infrastructures have been deployed and Traefik has been used as load balancer.

Interactive Development environment	● VScode and JupyterLab have been integrated as the two available interactive development environments (IDEs) and can be used throughout the platform. .
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Table 1: Components and actions: status and description. Green bullet: component ready; blue bullet: component under testing; orange bullet: component under development or is a prototype.

3.1 - DEVIATION FROM THE INITIAL ROADMAP

In the present section deviations from the initial roadmap proposed in D4.1 are described and justified.

3.1.1 - PaaS Orchestration and Provisioning

The following services and tools have not been included in the first release due to the fact that they are under development and will be included in the second release:

Federated service catalog: this component will replace the legacy Configuration Management Database (CMDB), implemented during the INDIGO-Datacloud project, and to store and manage the description of providers and their services (compute and storage) and resources, including virtual machine images, flavors, networks, etc.

Monitoring and Metering System: this component will be used in AI4EOSC to collect metrics from the federated providers in order to monitor their status and provide the Orchestrator with useful information for selecting the optimal deployment path.

Cloud Provider Ranker: this component will be improved by extending the ranking algorithm in order to take into account both the information coming from the Monitoring and Metering system and the dynamic resource availability at the different providers. This will improve the scheduling capabilities of the PaaS orchestrator, increasing the performance of the deployment workflow (reducing failures due to exceeded quotas, which require the automatic rescheduling of the request, resulting in delay).

Deviation does not impact the functionality delivered for the users.

3.1.2 - Federated Learning implementation

According to the first implementation plan (see D4.1), the component concerning federated training was due on month 19. Specifically, the deployment of federated learning training on the platform was planned for AI4EOSC 2.

However, as discussed in Section 2.5, this functionality is now ready to be used on the platform. This has been carried out in the first half of the project in order to be able to

make progress and improvements, for example in relation to client authentication on the platform.

The initial implementation plan established the need to carry out a careful analysis of the state of the art for the selection of the framework used. This analysis will continue to adapt to the rapid advances in the field, but for the first release, the first implementation and fine-tuning of the functionality, the Flower [26] Python library has been used.

3.2 - AI4EOSC 2 IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

Minimal deviations are expected for the AI4EOSC 2 release, apart from those highlighted in Section 3.2.

As already pointed out, the relevant activity concerns the **Federated Learning Trainings** component for which the implementation has been done and the functionality is ready for use. We are currently working on enabling client authentication with the server by means of secrets, in particular using Vault¹³ to allow generating new secrets if necessary, and revoking them in case of security breaches. In addition, in order to achieve this goal, some modifications have been done to the Flower library, which are deployed as extensions in a dedicated repository¹⁴.

4. - CONCLUSION

The present document is a demonstrator of the progress made within the AI4EOSC project to release the first version of the AI4EOSC platform (AI4EOSC 1). In section 2 the main components of the platform have been analyzed: Identity and Access Management (Section 2.1), the Workload Management System (Section 2.2), PaaS Orchestration and Provisioning (Section 2.3), the AI as a Service with a special focus in the deployment of the OSCAR cluster (Section 2.4), the Federated Learning trainings (Section 2.5) and the interactive development tools (Section 2.6).

As stated in D4.1 [1] *"in the first release of AI4EOSC, the goal is to eliminate dependencies inherited from the DEEP-HDC project by transitioning the existing stack to the new architecture"*, the activities carried out have been focused on the proper integration of those components carried out during the project activities to deploy a sustainable and interoperable platform. Having this objective in mind, we have been able to provide to the final users advanced tools aimed to carry out federated learning training on distributed data, performing inference, as well as an intuitive and user-friendly ecosystem for development purposes. Deviations from the initial plan are highlighted, including those in early advance, and justified where needed.

¹³ <https://www.vaultproject.io/>

¹⁴ <https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-flwr>

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